

ACINUPA FINAL REPORT 2009- 2010

ACINUPA

BY:
VERONICA PEREYRA
(CHAIRPERSON 2009-2010)

ACINUPA FINAL REPORT 2009-2010

INDEX

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I. INTRODUCTION : UN SPOUSE SUPPORT ANTECEDENTS

GLOBAL LEVEL

ACINUPA ANTECEDENTS

FOUNDATION

ACINUPA CHAIRPERSONS

II. ACINUPA: APRIL 2009 TO APRIL 2010

ELECTION OF NEW CHAIRPERSON

BOARD OF COORDINATORS

ACINUPA VOLUNTEERS 2009-2010

III. CONSTITUTION AND BY-LAWS

VI. ACINUPA LOGO

V. AREAS OF WORK

1) MIGRATION SUPPORT

WELCOME SUPPORT

PRELIMINARY CONTACT
INTERNET SUPPORT
WELCOME MEETINGS
INDUCTION TO PANAMA
MIGRATION WORKSHOP

DEPARTURE SUPPORT

2) NETWORKING

TEAM BUILDING

ACINUPA COMMUNITY BUILDING

COMMUNITY BUILDING ACTIVITIES

ACINUPA INFORMATION MANUAL

THREE ACINUPA BLOGS:

BLOG ACINUPA
UN INFORMATION MANUAL BLOG
INFORMATION MANUAL BLOG FOR EXPATRIATES

INTEGRATION WITH UN SYSTEM

ACINUPA VIDEO

UN ACOMMUNITY BUILDING ACTIVITIES

UN FAMILY DAY
UN EVENTS SUPPORTED BY ACINUPA
INTERAGENCY NETWORK OF EXPATRIATE FOCAL POINTS

NETWORKING WITH EXPATRIATES RESIDING IN PANAMA

INFORMATION MANUAL FOR EXPATRIATES OUTSIDE THE UN SYSTEM

MIGRATION WORKSHOPS

NETWORKING WITH THE PANAMANIAN COMMUNITY

NETWORKING WITH GESA (GLOBAL EXPATRIATE SPOUSE ASSOCIATION) AND OTHER LESAs (LOCAL EXPATRIATE SPOUSE ASSOCIATION)

3) SPOUSE EMPLOYMENT

a. JOB SEARCH SUPPORT (7 MODALITIES)

b. CAREER DEVELOPMENT WORKSHOPS

CAREER PLANNING

CVs AND RESUMES

INTERVIEW SKILLS

CORRESPONDENCE RELATED TO JOB SEARCH

NETWORKING RELATED TO JOB SEARCH

VI. CONCLUSIONS

VII. APPENDICES

- I. CONTITUTION AND BY-LAWS**
- II. NEW LOGO CONTEST CONDITIONS**
- III. COVER OF INFORMATION MANUAL 2010**
- IV. INDEX OF INFORMATION MANUAL**

“Because we believe in, work for and help build a more family-friendly UN.”

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

ACINUPA would like to express its special recognition to:

Nils Kastberg (former Director of UNICEF TACRO)

Bernt Aasen (present Director of UNICEF TACRO)

Gérard Gomez (OCHA Regional Director)

Marcela Suazo (Director of UNFPA LACRO)

Luis Mora (Deputy Director of UNFPA LACRO)

Joaquín Molina (Representative of PAHO/WHO)

Laura Flores (Deputy Representative of UNFPA Panama)

Freddy Justiniano (PNUD Regional Office)

Carlos Santos (UNEP Regional Office)

Jiesselinde González (UNIC Officer)

All the UN staff members, local and international, who have supported our Association during this period (April 2009-2010)

I. INTRODUCTION

◆ UN SPOUSE SUPPORT. ANTECEDENTS

GLOBAL LEVEL

- ◆ **1981: The UN General Assembly passes a Resolution (36/130) to promote work permits for expatriate spouses.**
- ◆ **1991: UNDP organizes a Conference on Spouse Employment and establishes the Spouse Employment Coordinators Programme.**
- ◆ **2003: Six Agencies (UNDP, UNFPA, UNICEF, UNOPS, WFP y WHO) launch the Dual Career and Staff Mobility Programme, later joined by UNAIDS and the World Bank.**
- ◆ **2003: UNDG launches the Dual Career and Staff Mobility Programme in a joint effort of six Agencies: UNDP, UNEPA, UNICEF, UNOPS, WFP y WHO, later joined by UNAIDS and the World Bank .**
- ◆ **2004: UNDG Joint Guidance Note on Expatriate Spouse Employment. Creation of LESAs (Local Expatriate Spouse Associations).**
- ◆ **2005-2007: 37 LESAs are created.**
- ◆ **2006: ACINUPA official beginning.**
- ◆ **2008: The Dual Career Programme begins to be included in the CEB (Chief Executive Board for Coordination Secretariat); later, ILO, UNESCO, UNHCR, UNRWA, UNWTO and the Secretary General join. Its Steering Committee is formed by representatives of the 14 Agencies of the UN System.**

◆ ACINUPA ANTECEDENTS

FOUNDATION

In December 2006, a group of UN spouses, led by Elizabeth Ugalde, officially launched ACINUPA (ASOCIACION DE CONYUGES Y PAREJAS DE FUNCIONARIOS(AS) INTERNACIONALES DE NACIONES UNIDAS EN PANAMA) with the support of the UN Resident Coordinator, Mr. José Eguren.

ACINUPA FOUNDERS

Elizabeth Ugalde

Ruth Sviercovich

Elena Euceda

Claudia Santos

Anne-Cécile Robin

Susana Vázquez Grassi

María Isabel Martínez

Jennifer Simpson

María Eugenia Mujica

◆ ACINUPA CHAIRPERSONS

DECEMBER 2006- FEBRUARY 2008:

ELIZABETH UGALDE
(Costa Rica)

MARCH 2008-APRIL 2009

RUTH SVIERCOVICH
(Ecuador)

APRIL 2009-APRIL 2010

VERONICA PEREYRA
(Argentina)

II. ACINUPA (APRIL 2009-APRIL 2010)

ELECTION OF A NEW CHAIRPERSON

On April 23rd 2009, the General Assembly of ACINUPA unanimously elected a new Chairperson: Verónica Pereyra. The new appointment was due to the departure of the previous Chairperson: Ruth Sviercovich.

BOARD OF COORDINATORS

The Coordinators previously appointed:
Elena Euceda (2007) and
Claudia Santos (2008)
continued in charge:

ACINUPA VOLUNTEERS 2009-2010

Alejandra Contreras
Carmen Urquiaga
Celia López Quintián
Edith Moya
Elaine Pinto

Elisabeth Schindler
Katia Cerra
Maylis de León
Susana Vázquez
Zianny Juárez

III. CONSTITUTION AND BY-LAWS

The first challenge this period faced was to write and pass ACINUPA Constitution and By-laws.

Among our members, there various lawyers and MAYLIS DE LEON generously undertook this task.

After a long time of research, corrections and revisions, ACINUPA finally approved and signed the final text of its CONSTITUTION AND BY-LAWS.

(See complete text in Appendix)

The full reinforcement of ACINUPA Constitution and By-laws will imply a gradual adaptation of the Association structure and of the increasing support that the UN System in Panama will provide the institution with.

IV. ACINUPA LOGO

ACINUPA needed a new logo updated to the UN regionalization process in which Panama had become site of an ever increasing UN System personnel with new Regional Agencies settling down in Ciudad del Saber.

While this new context meant a challenge for ACINUPA in terms of supporting the new families arriving in Panama, it also meant an opportunity to grow as an institution. Growth that had to be seen in a new logo.

Thence, ACINUPA decided to organize a logo contest. (See complete text of ACINUPA LOGO CONTEST TERMS in Appendix).

Susana Vázquez Grassi coordinated the process and generously devoted her energies to our Association.

Several proposals were presented. A five-members jury composed by UN senior officers and artists chose our present logo.

The winner design was a creation of Aleksandra Vdovic, who received her prize and recognition during the UN FAMILY DAY.

NEW LOGO CHOSEN BY THE JURY

OTHER LOGO DESIGNS

V. AREAS OF WORK

Three areas of work were identified at first:

- 1) **WELCOME SUPPORT (MIGRATION SUPPORT)**
- 2) **NETWORKING** and
- 3) **SPOUSE EMPLOYMENT.**

Though a welcome assistance had been stated at first, the need for a more comprehensive aid at the time of migration to and fro Panama soon became apparent. ACINUPA decided then to enhance the concept to Migration Support.

In this area, ACINUPA was extremely successful and a huge number of UN staff members and their families arriving in and leaving Panama could be helped.

For this success, various steps were taken to insure that ACINUPA support could be reached by most of the UN officers coming to Panama:

1. MIGRATION SUPPORT

- Personal and mail contact with HHRR officers of the Agencies,
- Contact with the UNDSS (United Nations Department of Safety and Security) to include information about our support,
- Contact with other LESAs (Local Expatriate Spouse Association) for them to inform about ACINUPA to its members;
- Contact with GESA (Global Expatriate Spouse Association) to publish information about our blogs and support in general
- Constant encouragement of ACINUPA members and some UN officers to let newcomers know about our support.

Of all these steps, the last one proved to be the most effective since a large proportion of ACINUPA new members had known about

our Association via personal contact in meetings.

◆ WELCOME SUPPORT

During this year, ACINUPA welcome support began as soon as the Association was informed that a new staff member had been assigned to Panama.

- ◆ **PRELIMINARY CONTACT:** When the first contact was made via email, a welcome letter and an ACINUPA form were sent as well as information about the two blogs: one including data about ACINUPA activities and events and the second one about living conditions in Panama.
- ◆ **INTERNET SUPPORT:** Whenever the UN staff member or his/her spouse or partner needed information or any support from ACINUPA, there was an immediate reply.

WELCOME MEETINGS

Every month, a meeting was organized to welcome newcomers; whenever necessary, a personal induction talk was coordinated.

INDUCTION TO PANAMA

In some cases, especially when the family had young children or was not hispanophone, an induction to Panama was provided with and the spouse or partners was taken on a tour around the city to show the different areas, shopping options, among others.

Preferably, the person in charge of this induction was chosen according to affinity with the newcomer: nationality, language, previous experience of the country of which the newcomer came from to facilitate the cultural shock process, among others.

This aid was particularly given to UNICEF TACRO families since there is a special agreement in this sense.

MIGRATION WORKSHOP

A migration workshop was periodically provided with by the Chairperson Verónica Pereyra.

This workshop aimed at helping the newly arrived in Panama (as well as those who were leaving the country) understand and facilitate the emotional process of moving to a new place, be it on the individual as well as the family level.

There were six migration workshops during the year, most of them in Spanish and one of them in French.

◆ DEPARTURE SUPPORT

Along this year, ACINUPA members who were leaving Panama received support for their moving process:

Apart from the Migration Workshop already mentioned above, ACINUPA carried out a research about the networking possibilities in the new place.

The following actions were taken:

- ◆ Contact with the LESA in the new country;
- ◆ Contact with GESA in case no LESA was available on the internet;
- ◆ Request of information about living conditions in the new country;
- ◆ Research among ACINUPA members to identify those families who had lived in the country of re-assignment;
- ◆ In case there was a member of ACINUPA who had lived in that country, coordination of a meeting with the parting member to receive induction to the new country;
- ◆ Reference letter in case of ACINUPA volunteers, stating the work he/she had performed in the Association;
- ◆ Farewell meeting and gift;
- ◆ Networking soon after departure;
- ◆ Support at the event of a natural catastrophe.

2.NETWORKING

The second area of work along this year was NETWORKING and most of the human resources and energies were invested into this area in order to build and improve:

- ◆ the ACINUPA team of volunteers,
- ◆ a community of members,
- ◆ integration with UN Agencies in Panama,
- ◆ mutual support with expatriate groups residing in Panama;
- ◆ a relation of integration into the Panamanian community and
- ◆ mutual support with other LESAs.

◆ TEAM BUILDING

A long process had to be implemented in order to transform the board of three Coordinators and some generous volunteers that ran ACINUPA one year ago into the strong and engaged ACINUPA volunteer task groups that are now taking the administration of the institution on April 23rd 2010.

Such process implied a sustained effort of communication and networking. The first semester was almost entirely performed by the Chairperson, Verónica Pereyra.

Working meetings, informal gatherings, social events were organized as well as coordination of volunteers for the different activities had to be carried out along this year.

In the last semester, Celia López Quintián and Susana Vázquez Grassi have made a vital contribution taking increasing responsibilities in the management of the two ACINUPA mail accounts.

◆ BUILDING THE ACINUPA COMMUNITY

Susana Vázquez also helped to build a data base in which all information about each member of our Association was made available in order to create networks according to affinity.

At present, every member who joins ACINUPA is given a list of contacts who share profession, nationality and a family in with children of similar age.

UN staff members who come without their families are also supported if they request to become part of our Association.

Emphasis is given to assist, whenever requested, UN personnel who are single parents as well as non Spanish-speaking staff members.

Some initiatives have been repeatedly proposed and are pending to be undertaken for the next executive committee. Among them:

A security network among spouses and partners (already discussed about with UNDSS)

- ❖ Day care in emergencies
- ❖ Play dates (age group activities) for children of members
- ❖ Male members group
- ❖ Monthly meetings to follow up the process of adaptation to Panama
- ❖ Member counseling

❖ COMMUNITY BUILDING ACTIVITIES

As already stated, ACINUPA organized during this year a variety of community building activities, be them monthly socializing meetings, informal gatherings, social events, city tours, lectures, cultural events, among others.

Katia Cerra was the volunteer who enthusiastically organized most of these activities.

TOUR TO CASCO VIEJO

ACINUPA PRESENT AT ART EXHIBITION

TOUR TO OLD PANAMA

UNSS SECURITY TALK FOR ACINUPA

BIRTHDAY CELEBRATION

SOCIALIZATION MEETINGS

ACINUPA INFORMATION MANUAL

One key tool to build a sense of community was the publication of the ACINUPA INFORMATION MANUAL entirely written by ACINUPA volunteers but with the impulse of Freddy Justiniano (UNDP Regional Office).

Begun some time ago by Elizabeth Ugalde, Ruth Sviercovich, Anne-Cécile Robin, Elena Euceda, Claudia Santos and Susana Vázquez, the INFORMATION MANUAL was finally completed and revised by Susana Vázquez, Tsveti Berthin, and Verónica Pereyra.

(SEE LIST OF CONTENTS OF INFORMATION MANUAL AT THE APPENDIX)

LINK: <http://acinupainfo.canalblog.com>

ACINUPA BLOGS

A) ACINUPA BLOG

During this year, the ACINUPA blog, created by Marjolein Jacobs, began to be updated on a regular basis and to include all the activities and community events to come or a report of them as well as advertisements and other useful information.

The task of updating this blog was a responsibility of Verónica Pereyra at first but Elisabeth Schindler took it in charge and will go on updating all ACINUPA blogs during the next period.

It must be said that a previous version of the blog had to be completely erased for the sake of security. Having consulted with UNDSS, ACINUPA resumed the task avoiding all mention of names, even places and times if necessary.

LINK: <http://acinupa.canalblog.com>

B) WELCOME TO PANAMA. INFORMATION MANUAL BLOG

It includes information about the living conditions in Panama housing, moving process, medical services and household services, immunities and privileges due to the status of International Mission, among others). This blog is also used by all UN System staff personnel.

LINK: <http://acinupainfo.canalblog.com>

C) WELCOME TO PANAMA. BLOG OF THE ACINUPA INFORMATION MANUAL FOR EXPATRIATES OUTSIDE THE UN SYSTEM

LINK: <http://acinupainfopanam.canalblog.com>

(dealt with underneath)

◆ INTEGRATION WITH UNITED NATIONS SYSTEM IN PANAMA

During the period covered by this Report, ACINUPA has kept a fluid exchange of information with the Agencies of the UN System in Panama.

ACINUPA has considered along this year that an optimal relation with the UN Agencies in Panama could only be possible by making the Association known in all its contributions to the well being of UN families.

◆ ACINUPA VIDEO

Thence, taking into account that ACINUPA vision and mission needed to be more widely known at all levels of the UN System, the first initiative the new ACINUPA took was the editing of a video in which spouses' opinions and testimonies were reflected.

This was a pioneer experience among the LESAs of the world: for the first time, the needs and potentialities of UN expatriate spouses were expressed from an institution.

A group of volunteers gave their views of the migrant life that a UN family faces, its advantages and drawbacks; the consequences in the development of a family project and the challenges to continue a professional career in a constantly changing scenario. Likewise, two UN officers: Enrique Paz (UNICEF TACRO) and Cecilia Maurente (UNFPA LACRO) emphasized on the importance of the support that ACINUPA can mean to the UN personnel who arrive with their families as well as to the UN staff members who arrive alone and face two challenges: the adaptation to the new position and the logistics of settling down in Panama. Finally, Nils Kastberg, former UNICEF TACRO Director, highlighted the

urgent need of supporting spouse associations as a means of fulfilling the UN mandate of making the UN System more family-friendly.

The ACINUPA video has played an important role in the identification of our Association as a key element to improve the UN concept of family-friendly Agencies and life/work balance.

This video was shown at the Regional Director Team (RDT) Meeting that was carried out in July in Panama. The idea was welcome by the Regional Directors of most Agencies and copies of the video were distributed among the members of the RDT.

Furthermore, GESA (Global Expatriate Spouse Association) shown the ACINUPA video in Geneva and published it in its web page.

Along this year, ACINUPA has given copies of the video to Regional Directors, Deputy Regional Directors and Representatives of several Agencies of the UN System in Panama.

UN COMMUNITY BUILDING ACTIVITIES

Our Association has also coordinated different activities to integrate the families of the all the Agencies of the UN System in Panama.

UN FAMILY DAY

In the first place, our UN FAMILY DAY must be mentioned.

On October 23rd, the UN FAMILY DAY, entirely and generously carried out by the ACINUPA volunteers, was a total success.

On that day, more than three hundred people gathered to know each other, share international food of more than twenty countries and win prizes in the raffle. UN staff members, alone or with their families, expatriate and local staff could also enjoy Panamanian dances; children had a moppets show by Carmen Urquiaga.

Likewise, diplomas and recognitions were given to the participants of the ACINUPA LOGO CONTEST as well as the winner of the Contest.

The ACINUPA volunteers organized every aspect of the event: they designed and printed the UN FAMILY DAY poster and the entrance tickets, the Diplomas to be given at the ceremony; also, they advertised the event in all the Agencies via mail and personally; they prepared traditional dishes from their homeland, decorated the tables, donated raffle prizes, wrote the moppets show, staged it. Finally, they prepared a presentation about our Association to be known by the rest of the UN System.

GIFTS AND ACINUPA BANNER

TRADITIONAL CUISINE FROM 22 COUNTRIES

PANAMANIAN DANCES PRESENT

Likewise, initiatives organized by UN Agencies or UN staff members have been adopted and promoted by ACINUPA in many different ways: 1) via email forwarding to active members and honorary members, 2) advertising the activities on our blogs, 3) calls for massive attendance and 4) active participation as volunteer workers.

INTERNATIONAL WOMEN'S DAY (UNFPA PANAMA) 1

INTERNATIONAL DAY OF HUMAN RIGHTS

ACINUPA SUPPORTING PAHO CAMPAIGN

INTERNATIONAL HEALTH DAY

SOME UN EVENTS SUPPORTED BY ACINUPA

**PAHO/WHO:
INTERNATIONAL HEALTH DAY**

UNHCHR: INTERNATIONAL HUMAN RIGHTS DAY

UNHCR Panama: INTERNATIONAL DAY OF REFUGEES

UNFPA Panama: INTERNATIONAL POPULATION DAY

INTERNATIONAL WOMEN'S DAY THEATRE PRESENTATION

UNEP: FILM HOME

VIGIL AGAINST CLIMATE CHANGE

**MILLENNIUM DEVELOPMENT GOALS:
STAND UP AGAINST POVERTY
CAMPAIGN**

❖ INTERAGENCY NETWORK OF EXPATRIATE FOCAL POINTS

One key achievement was the construction of a network of Expatriate Focal Points for ACINUPA in various Agencies. This network will support the next executive committee enriching our views and possibilities.

UNDP Regional Office: Gert Danielsen

UNICEF TACRO: María Elena Solano

UNIFEM: Nadine Gasman

**OCHA Regional Office: Virginia Pérez
Dovale**

UNOPS Regional Office: Alicia Escurrell

Monthly meetings are planned with the ACINUPA executive committee in order to implement a common policy supporting the UNDG Joint Guidance Note on Spouse Employment (2004) as well as other UN documents promoting Family/Work Balance and a UN with more family-friendly initiatives.

◆ SUPPORT TO EXPATRIATE GROUPS RESIDING IN PANAMA

During this year, ACINUPA has actively supported different groups of expatriate citizens residing in Panama.

Information Manual for expatriates outside the UN system

ACINUPA created a blog in order to provide with information about the living conditions in Panama for expatriates that do not belong to the UN System.

This blog can be consulted at the following link:

<http://acinupainfopanam.canalblog.com>

(SEE INDEX OF THE INFORMATION CONTAINED IN BLOGS AT THE APPENDIX)

Migration Workshop

The ACINUPA Migration Workshop was coordinated by Verónica Pereyra to:

- A. Union France Panama
- B. Círculo Argentino Panameño
- C. Círculo de Mujeres Mexicanas Panameñas

The Annual Solidarity Event (Caravana de la Solidaridad) organized by the Diplomatic Ladies in Panama to help local community services and charities was also promoted by ACINUPA and received a massive response from our members.

During this period, ACINUPA organized an active outreach service that built new networks among expatriates living in Panama. Information was exchanged with different groupings and institutions like:

- WHO'S NEW (a group of international women)
- Expatriate Explorers
- Union France Panama (UFP)
- Círculo Argentino Panameño
- Asociación China de Mujeres Ejecutivas
- Asociación de Profesionales Chinos en Panamá
- Asociación de Damas Mexicanas
- Lycée Français Paul Gauguin
- Instituto Griego Atenea

AT THE JAPANESE TEA CEREMONY
(RESIDENCE OF THE AMBASSADOR OF JAPAN)

PROMOTING THE INTERNATIONAL HEALTH DAY AT THE FRENCH LYCEUM
(TOGETHER WITH UFP MEMBERS)

AT THE UFP GALA TO FUND THE FRENCH LYCEUM

AT THE BIOMUSEUM WITH UFP

◆ INTEGRATION INTO THE PANAMANIAN CONTEXT

All along the year, ACINUPA has invested resources in order to begin an institutional process of integration into the local community. Being certain that a mutual enrichment will be the final output, contacts have been made with different groups and associations.

WITH PANAMANIAN CIVIL PROTECTION STAFF

SHARING CINTA COSTERA FOR INTERNATIONAL HEALTH DAY

ACINUPA MUPPETS FOR PANAMANIAN CHILDREN

ACINUPA Y UNICEF TACRO SUPPORTING PANAMANIAN ART (MR. BERNT AASEN, REG. DIR. UNICEF TACRO AND ACINUPA MEMBERS)

ACINUPA PARTICIPATION IN INTERNATIONAL WOMEN' DAY

◆ NETWORKING WITH GESA (LOCAL EXPATRIATE SPOUSE ASSOCIATION) AND LESAs (LOCAL EXPATRIATE SPOUSE ASSOCIATION)

NETWORKING WITH GESA

GESA was originally founded in Rome though it has moved to Geneva in 2009. It keeps a web page with some information about the different LESAs of the world.

ACINUPA has sent GESA information about the new Chairperso, two articles to be published in the GESA Newsletter, the ACINUPA INFORMATION MANUAL as well as the links to our three blogs. The response to this input remains a challenge for ACINUPA's next Executive Committee.

NETWORKING WITH LESAs

Being Panama site to various UN Regional Offices, ACINUPA has led the process of establishing mutual support with other LESAs of the Latin American and Caribbean countries..

Likewise, as a result of the support granted to members reassigned in other regions of the world, ACINUPA has exchanged information with other LESAs in North America, Africa and Europe.

- UNHONLESA (Honduras)
- UNCHILESA (Chile)
- UNGUALESA (Guatemala)
- LESA ROMA (Rome)
- UNKLESA (Kenia)
- NYLESA (New York)

The ACINUPA INFORMATION MANUAL was sent to all the LESAs appearing at the GESA web page.

Contacts were made in order to help found or strengthen LESAs in: Ecuador, Dominican Republic (with UN staff members assigned to Haiti due to the earthquake emergency), Jamaica and Bolivia.

3. SPOUSE EMPLOYMENT SUPPORT

During the period April 2009-April 2010, the third area of work of ACINUPA has consisted in the promotion of all activities and initiatives leading to open career opportunities for spouses and partners as well as training opportunities or professional positions.

ACINUPA has helped its members in their job search taking the following actions:

1. Job search support with research on vacancies within and outside the UN System in Panama;
2. Forwarding of vacancies sent by HHRR in the different Agencies as well as other multilateral institutions, international and local NGOs,. Celia López Quintián and Susana Vázquez were in charge of this support.
3. Sending CVs and Resumes to prospective employers;
4. Addressing CVs and Resumes to international HHRR enterprises and head hunters. Zianny Juárez led this initiative.
5. Supporting the candidature of ACINUPA members to vacancies in the UN System on the grounds that “among equally well-qualified candidates, a UN spouse should be priority” complying with the UNDG Joint Guidance Note on Spouse Employment (2004);
6. Coordinating language lessons for ACINUPA members as well as UN staff members. Kristina Carrizosa, member of ACINUPA, was the lecturer in charge of this training activity.
7. Teaching FIVE Career Development Workshops:
 - i. Career Planning
 - ii. CVs and Resumes
 - iii. Interview Skills
 - i. Correspondence related to job search
 - ii. Networking related to job search

CAREER DEVELOPMENT WORKSHOPS

ACINUPA coordinated five Career Development Workshops for its members. The activity was organized and taught by Verónica Pereyra with the support of Susana Vázquez and Nancy Andrade.

CAREER PLANNING WORKSHOP

CAREER PLANNING

CVs AND RESUMES

INTERVIEW SKILLS

CORRESPONDENCE RELATED TO JOB SEARCH

NETWORKING RELATED TO JOB SEARCH

CAREER DEVELOPMENT WORKSHOP

Each Workshop consisted in three parts:

- ❖ Presentation of the theoretical background
- ❖ Work experience by a senior ACINUPA member
- ❖ Personalized coaching of the participants

ENGLISH CLASSES FOR ACINUPA MEMBERS

INTERVIEW SKILLS WORKSHOP

LANGUAGE COURSE FOR ACINUPA MEMBERS

VI. TO CONCLUDE

The period from April 2009 to April 2010 has meant hard work as well as a harvest of achievements and growth for ACINUPA.

Our Association has begun to show the astonishing difference that a group of volunteers can make in the well being of the UN expatriate families and thence of the UN international personnel.

An organizational structure and a team of volunteer have been built; a legal framework, expertise and know-how that will guide the next Executive Committee have also been provided with; networks at local and international levels have been formed; a warm and friendly support for newcomers has been assured.

ACINUPA has become a model for most spouse associations in the world.

The UN System in Panama has witnessed ACINUPA grow and make valuable contributions and it has benefited from those initiatives.

Now it is time to go even further...

Panama, 22nd April 2010

Verónica Pereyra

ACINUPA Chairperson (2009-2010)

VII. APPENDICES

- I. CONSTITUTION AND BY-LAWS**
- II. NEW LOGO CONTEST CONDITIONS**
- III. COVER OF INFORMATION MANUAL:
WELCOME TO PANAMA 2010**
- IV. INDEX OF INFORMATION MANUAL**

Appendix I

CONSTITUTION & BY-LAWS

Ratified and adopted by the General Membership Meeting on

26th November 2009 in Panama

Article I Nature and Objectives

Article II Membership

Article III Structure

Article IV Management of affairs

Article V Meetings

Article VI Quorum

Article VII Elections

Article VIII Term of office

Article IX Vacancies

Article X Financial operations

Article XI Advisory Council

Article XII Amendments

Article XIII Ratification and Adoption

ARTICLE I - NATURE AND OBJECTIVES

Section 1

- a) The Name of the Association shall be ACINUPA (Asociación de Cónyuges y Parejas de Funcionarios (as) Internacionales de NNUU en Panamá), the translation of which would be: United Nations Expatriate Spouses and Partners' Association in Panama.
- b) ACINUPA is established in the Ciudad de Panama, Panama; headquarter of several UN Regional, Sub-regional and National Agencies, in accordance with the UNDG Joint Guidance Note on the Employment of Expatriate Spouses, July 2004, hereafter referred to as "The Guidance Note".
- c) ACINUPA will operate within the United Nations System and will not be registered as a Panamanian association.
- d) ACINUPA shall be a non-profit and non-governmental group.
- e) ACINUPA shall be affiliated with an appropriate body or existing similar organization recognized by United Nations Headquarters in New York, the UN-GESA, or if practicable, is directly affiliated with the United Nations itself or to its authorized Specialized Agencies in the region.
- f) The association shall be created for an indefinite term.
- g) As an association formed by high-mobility members with limited availability due to their family and employment duties, ACINUPA foresees that all activities and procedures will allow a sensible flexibility.

Therefore, the following articles should be understood as suggested guidelines subject to the revisions that a changing membership demands.

Section 2

The primary objectives of the ACINUPA shall be:

- Promote spouses and partners' employment in all aspects: career planning, training, lobbying, finding jobs in Panama, identifying opportunities of recruitment, among others.

- Support arriving UN families settle into their new duty stations in Panama.
- Networking for the mutual benefit of all its members.
-

Therefore, the association will

- Promote the continuous exchange of information and access to quality employment, inside of the United Nations as well as outside the system, for the spouses and partners of UN expatriate functionaries who have professional career aspirations.
- Identify the priority concerns and interests of expatriate spouses and define an annual work plan addressing them. Work groups can be designated to develop the priority objectives of the work plan.
- Liaise with other local expatriate spouse groups and associations, particularly from foreign services, the diplomatic community and multinational institutions to promote collaboration and exchange of information;
- Hold periodic meetings of Association members to review progress, discuss new initiatives, develop new strategies, define or revise assignments. Report periodically or on an ad hoc basis to the UN/GESA on activities undertaken.
- Submit to the UN/GESA the agreed program of work and an annual report of accomplishments;
- Make available and keep current in cooperation with all UN (related)-Agencies a “Welcome Package” material for newly arrived expatriate spouses that include information on the services available in the country, family support network and organizations, and any other such information as may be deemed relevant.
- Generally assist newly-arrived expatriate spouses in settling down in the country by providing appropriate information and advice, including by facilitating the early identification of employment opportunities for expatriate spouses.
- Foment the participation of the ACINUPA Members in workshops, conferences, seminars and training courses promoted through the United Nations System.
- i.

ARTICLE II - MEMBERSHIP

Section 1

Regular and Associated Membership

Regular Membership shall be open to all spouses of expatriate UN staff members from all Agencies, programmes and offices affiliated with the UN based in Panama and other parts of Panama. For the purpose of determining who is eligible to be a member of the Association, the relevant definition of spouse and partner shall be found in the staff regulations for the organization or Agency of the staff member.

Associated membership shall be open to all non-resident spouses before coming to Panama in anticipation of their transfer. Associated members shall have some of the privileges of regular members but shall have no voting rights or the right to hold an elected or nominated office. However, upon arrival in Panama an associated member must convert the membership into a regular status.

Section 2

Begin and End of Membership

A member shall only become a bona fide member upon submission of the membership application form approved by the Membership Committee or the Board. The membership ends automatically at the end of each fiscal year (31.December) and has to be renewed each year by validating/ updating the given membership information;

A member shall lose his/her membership upon termination of the spouse’s employment/service contract with the United Nations and its Agencies. In the case of death of or divorce from the member’s spouse, the member shall be allowed to continue his/her regular membership status, unless he/she voluntarily resigns. However, validity of membership shall always cover up to the end of the fiscal year.

In the event that a regular member (spouse) is hired by any UN agency, such member shall also be allowed to retain his/her regular membership status, unless he/she voluntarily relinquishes such status.

Any member may tender written resignation to the Association for whatever reasons she/he may have.

Any member shall be subjected to expulsion proceedings for willful violation of the Constitution & By-laws or for acts inimical or detrimental to the reputation of the Association.

Section 3

Membership fees and dues

The membership of the ACINUPA shall be not free of charge.

A one-time non-reimbursable annual membership fee, to defray expenses relative to the legitimate affairs of the Association, shall be determined by the Board and be approved by the General Assembly. Special levies and reasonable fees may be assessed and collected from the members to defray expenses for valid and licit special purposes or activities of the Association. Also this shall be determined by the Board and be approved by the General Assembly.

An inter-agency financial support according to the amount of expatriate staff members of each UN Agency will be envisaged in the future.

Section 4

Members Rights and Obligations

A member has the following rights and obligations in the Association:

Rights of members are

- to participate in all legitimate affairs of the Association;
- to vote and to be voted in any of its elections ;
- to participate in and to be appointed as spokesperson of any grouping or committee of his/her choice within the Association;
- to have access to the official records of the Association subject to its rules and regulations ;
- to be informed of all vital information concerning the affairs of the Association;
- to request assistance from the ACINUPA Board and Workgroup members
- to have such other rights inherent to a member of an Association;

Obligations of members are:

- to support the cause of the Association and to respect the By-Laws;
- to fill out and submit a membership form and to renew the membership each year;
- to submit all necessary data in order to be included in the ACINUPA data base;
- to actively participate in the research of information and job opportunities while living in the country;
- to elect the Executive Committee's member each year;
- to take note of ACINUPA activities, propose programs and projects to the association through open discussion, debate, motions, and voting for adoption;
- to attend regularly all meetings of the Association unless her/his absence is justifiable;
- to respond to membership surveys;
- to notify the Chairperson about hiring and before departure of the country;
- to pay diligently dues or other special levies if indicated;
- to observe proper behavior as expected of a decent member of the Association and avoid actions that are inimical to its reputation;
- to report to the Membership Assembly any knowledge of fraudulent activities of any officer or member which are inimical to the Association;
- to perform such other duties and responsibilities required of a member of an Association.

ARTICLE III - STRUCTURE

ACINUPA shall be guided by:

- Executive Committee**
- Board**
- Work Groups**
- The General Assembly**

ARTICLE IV - MANAGEMENT OF AFFAIRS

Section 1

Executive Committee

Chairperson

Coordinator (welcome services and social networking)

Coordinator (dual career and general networking)

Secretary

Treasurer

Section 2

Board

Section 3

Workgroups or Working Committees

Section 4

General Assembly

ARTICLE V - MEETINGS

Section 1

There shall be four (4) categories of the Association's meetings, namely:

1. **Regular meetings** - meetings of the Board, the working groups, the membership events- in the ordinary course of business of the Association;

Regular meetings shall be held at least once a month in a designated place and time. Notice of these meetings including a draft agenda shall be communicated between its members in writing at least 5 days prior to the meeting, and published on the ACINUPA blog.

2. **Cooperation meetings** - meetings of the Board with UN-Focal Points to harmonize and secure progress on the implementation of "The Guidance Note".

Cooperation meetings shall be held at least bi-monthly in a designated place and time. Notice of these meetings including a draft agenda and attachments shall be communicated between its members in writing at least 7 days prior to the meeting, and published on the ACINUPA website.

3. **Special meetings**- meetings called for specific purposes; Special Meetings shall be called for specific purposes by the Board with the concurrence of at least simple majority (half + 1) of its members as in the case of Board meetings; and in the case of General Membership meetings, the concurrence of ten (10) bona fide regular members in a written notice addressed to the Board for their approval, specifying the urgent purposes. Due to the urgent nature of these meetings the notice including a draft agenda and necessary attachments shall be communicated between its members in writing at least 5 days prior to the meeting.

4. **Annual General Membership meetings**- meetings of the General Assembly to be attended by all members of the Association. The General Assembly meets at least once a year for the annual election and approval of the work plan in a designated place and time. The notice of the meeting and its agenda shall be sent to all members at least one (1) month prior to the meeting.

Section 2

All meetings shall be made public to all members via the ACINUPA blog.

Section 3

Suggested monthly schedule for meetings

Week 1: Board meeting

Week 2: Work Group meetings

Week 3: Membership events

Week 4: Bimonthly Board with Focal points / additional Work Group meetings/ other

ARTICLE VI - QUORUM IN THE MEETING

Section 1

In order to validly transact the affairs of the Association

- one-half (1/2) plus 1 of all the Board members shall constitute quorum in the meetings of the Board
- 10% of all the members but at least a minimum of 20 members of the Association shall constitute quorum in the Annual General Membership meetings and Special Membership meetings

Section 2

The Quorum in every meeting shall be determined by the physical count of all the members present in the meeting and compared to the total number of members of the Association respectively of the Board. In meetings where proxy voting is involved, quorum shall be determined by the total number of present members plus (+) the total number of duly -accomplished proxies and compared to the total number of members of the Association/ the Board.

Section 3

In Work Group meetings, simple majority (half +1) of all its members shall constitute quorum in order to validly transact the affairs of the Work Group.

ARTICLE VII - ELECTIONS

Section 1

The election of officers shall be held annually during the Annual General Membership Meeting on the 1st Friday of December of each fiscal year in a designated place and time;

Section 2

The election shall be conducted and supervised by the Election Committee, who shall receive and solicit nominations from the membership for each office to be held and presented to the Membership Assembly for actual voting as provided for by this Constitution & By-Laws. The board shall appoint an Election Committee composed of a minimum of two bona fide members latest two month before the Annual General Membership Meeting.

Section 3

Any regular member of the Association may run and become an Officer provided she/he agrees to be a candidate for the board and to assume the duties of the position. Individual members may nominate themselves for office. A nomination form for all candidates must be completed, with two supporting member signatures, which will be designated by the Election Committee. The list of candidates shall be published on the web-site ideally one month prior to Annual General Membership Meeting for consideration by the membership.

Section 4

The election proceedings shall be conducted either by a) secret ballots or by b) open votes subject to the consent of the majority of members. The officers shall be elected individually. Proxy voting shall be allowed on the election date with the written authorization of the member who will be absent. Absentee voting may be done per email, prior to the election date based on current nominations at that time. Members voting by absentee ballot or by proxy should note that nominations will be accepted at the Annual General Membership Meeting.

ARTICLE VIII - TERM OF OFFICE

Section 1

The officers of the association shall be elected for one year. No member shall serve more than two consecutive terms on the Board. A member shall stand down for at least one year before being eligible for re-election or re-nomination to a Board position.

Section 2

The regular term of office or cycle of the Association shall start from January 1 and ends at December of each year.

For any other reason: The term of office shall begin on the 1st day of the month following the Annual General Membership Meeting, and shall expire at the end of the month in which the successive Annual General Membership Meeting has taken place, or until her/his successor shall have been duly elected.

Section 3

If a member is appointed/elected for less than 4 months officer, that period shall not be counted as a term, and hence, the member shall be eligible for the next two consecutive terms on the Board.

ARTICLE IX - VACANCIES

Section 1

In the event permanent vacancy shall exist in the elective positions, by reasons of death, resignation or removal from the office, such vacancy shall be filled up by a Special election during a meeting to be called for such purpose. The meeting should be scheduled within a month after the vacancy

occurred. For the meantime until the election, the board might appoint an interim officer for this position. The elected member must serve the unexpired portion of the former board member.

Section 2

Whenever a member serving in a position on the Board is absent for three consecutive months without leaving an appointed delegate to fulfill her/his duties, the Board member is considered resigned and the position will be automatically considered vacant. The Board will proceed to appoint another member to fill the vacancy on the Board by the fourth month.

Section 3

No members shall hold more than one office on the Board, and no member shall serve more than two consecutive terms on the Board. A member shall stand down for at least one year before being eligible for re-election or re-nomination to a Board position.

ARTICLE X - FINANCIAL OPERATIONS & PROCEDURES

Section 1

The Vice Chair Treasurer, who might appoint her/his Assistant Treasurer from among the regular members, shall handle the financial operations of the Association. Every receipt and disbursement of funds shall be properly recorded and accounted for.

Section 2

No member of the ACINUPA including Board members shall commit the Association to any event involving finances or financing without the express approval of the Board. For any financial disbursement, the Board must approve an express range of expenditure.

Section 3

The officers of the Executive Committee shall have the authority to handle checking account procedures.

Section 4

Periodic financial reports shall be prepared for monitoring purposes and for determination of the financial position or status of the Association, which must be certified for its correctness by the Vice Chair Treasurer. These reports shall include all funds granted to the Association such as access to seminars and workshops, etc. and how these funds were made available to the membership.

Section 5

The Association shall not be under obligation to pay for any financial transactions fraudulently entered into by its officers and members beyond their authority. All individual members of the Association shall in no case be subject to/or liable for any financial obligations other than the regular dues or special levies for reasonable specific purposes.

Section 6

The Board shall have the ACINUPA accounts audited each year by an independent auditor who shall neither be an officer nor member the Association, and shall volunteer his/her services. The selection of the independent auditor shall be approved by the Board prior to the annual audit. The auditor shall report the results in writing to the Board, which then will be presented to the membership as early in the year as possible before the annual meeting.

ARTICLE XI - THE ADVISORY COUNCIL

Section 1

The Board might approve an Advisory Council, which will serve as an advisory body on all matters concerning the Association and the running of its affairs.

Section 2

The Council shall be composed of at least three (3) members who are knowledgeable in the fields of finance, law, organizational structures and affairs and other specialized fields of knowledge, who may not necessarily be a member of this Association and shall be chosen by the Board. Past Chairpersons of the Association shall automatically be members of this body.

Section 3

The Council shall meet on specific purpose/s to act on all organizational matters referred to them by the Board or by the members.

ARTICLE XII - AMENDMENTS

ANEXO: FORMULARIO DE MEMBRESIA DE ACINUPA

ACINUPA

ASOCIACION DE CONYUGES Y PAREJAS DE FUNCIONARIOS (AS) INTERNACIONALES DE NACIONES UNIDAS EN PANAMA

La información que se solicita a continuación será usada únicamente por la Asociación para los fines establecidos en sus objetivos. La información recolectada es confidencial. Por favor, sea conciso y claro en sus respuestas.

DATOS PERSONALES

NOMBRE Y APELLIDO			
NACIONALIDAD			
LUGAR DE NACIMIENTO			
FECHA DE NACIMIENTO			
SEXO	F	M	
NÚMERO DE HIJOS		FECHA DE NACIMIENTO DE LOS HIJOS:	
NOMBRE CONYUGE		AGENCIA PARA LA QUE TRABAJA	
FECHA DE ARRIBO			

CONTACTOS

E-MAIL	
TELÉFONO CASA	
CELULAR	

DATOS PROFESIONALES

PROFESIÓN	
-----------	--

ÁREAS DE EXPERIENCIA LABORAL	
IDIOMAS QUE HABLA	
IDIOMA MATERNO	OTROS
OTRAS HABILIDADES Y APTITUDES	

DATOS LABORALES

TRABAJA ACTUALMENTE	SI		NO	
DÓNDE (Marque con una X)	SECTOR PRIVADO	GOBIERNO	ONG	SNU
TIEMPO PARCIAL	TIEMPO COMPLETO			
TRABAJO REMUNERADO:	TRABAJO VOLUNTARIADO:			

SI NO TRABAJA ACTUALMENTE:

DESEA TRABAJAR?	SI	NO
DISPOSICIÓN DEL TIEMPO	PARCIAL	COMPLETO
LE INTERESA EL TRABAJO VOLUNTARIO?	SI	NO

ACERCA DE ACINUPA:

LE GUSTARIA PARTICIPAR ACTIVAMENTE EN ACINUPA?			
SI		NO	
EN QUÉ ÁREA LE GUSTARÍA COLABORAR?			
APOYO A RECIÉN LLEGADOS			
ACTIVIDADES SOCIALES Y DE VOLUNTARIADO			
INTERESES LABORALES			

APPENDIX II

CONCURSO DE LOGOTIPO ACINUPA

Asociación de Cónyuges y Parejas de Funcionarios(as) Internacionales de Naciones Unidas en Panamá

CONSIDERANDO QUE, en estos últimos dos años, el Sistema de Naciones Unidas en Panamá se ha transformado significativamente con la llegada de numerosas Oficinas Regionales y Subregionales de las distintas Agencias y que, por ello, ACINUPA está constituido en su mayoría por cónyuges y parejas de esos funcionarios regionales y sub-regionales,

TENIENDO EN CUENTA que el antiguo logo de nuestra Asociación refleja una realidad que no se corresponde con las circunstancias presentes de ACINUPA y aún menos, con la dimensión que alcanzará en un futuro próximo, con la llegada de nuevos funcionarios regionales y sub-regionales,

ACINUPA (Asociación de Cónyuges y Parejas de Funcionarios (as) Internacionales de Naciones Unidas en Panamá) **RESUELVE** convocar a concurso en búsqueda de un nuevo logotipo ilustrativo que identifique a la Asociación en su rol actual a la vez que refleje clara y plenamente su aporte a las NNUU, su objetivo y misión.

Bases del Concurso

1.- REQUISITOS DE PARTICIPACIÓN:

- Podrán postularse personas mayores de 14 años de cualquier nacionalidad, siempre que uno de los miembros de su familia pertenezca al Sistema de las Naciones Unidas.
- No podrán participar en el concurso miembros del jurado calificador de los trabajos sometidos
- Cuando el trabajo sea realizado en equipo, se deberán incluir a los/las principales colaboradores/as. Un equipo consistirá de un máximo de 2 personas.
- Cada participante podrá presentar hasta tres logotipos.

2.- PRESENTACION DEL TRABAJO

- La presentación del trabajo será anónima.
- En un sobre grande cerrado, donde conste el pseudónimo del/a autor/a, se incluirá:
 - 1) los trabajos, que deben ser presentados en forma impresa (tamaño 8 x 10 pulgadas) y electrónica (CD) con una resolución de al menos 300 DPI y
 - 2) un sobre cerrado con el pseudónimo en cuyo interior se especificará el pseudónimo, el nombre completo del/a autor/a, dirección electrónica y números de teléfono residencial y celular.
- Se exige que todos/as los/as participantes certifiquen que el trabajo presentado sea original, más allá de los procesos normales de edición.
- Los/las participantes deberán quedarse con copias de los trabajos presentados, pues los mismos no serán devueltos.
- Los trabajos serán entregados en las **oficinas de ACINUPA (Edificio de UNICEF-TACRO, 2do. Piso, Avenida Morse, Ciudad del Saber) los días 29 y 30 de septiembre del 2009 en el horario de 9:00 a 12:00 y de 14:00 a 16:00 junto con el pago de una inscripción al concurso por un valor de 10 dólares americanos.**

3.- PROCESO DE SELECCIÓN

- El jurado estará compuesto por:
 - dos coordinadores de ACINUPA
 - un funcionario de NNUU
 - un creativo de audiovisuales
 - un artista plástico
- El jurado evaluará los trabajos presentados y elegirá a un/a ganador/a.
- El jurado puede tomar la decisión de no conceder el premio y declarar desierto el concurso.
- Los jurados tienen derecho a rechazar un trabajo que, en su opinión, no cumple con los requisitos del concurso
- En caso de que se presente algún cuestionamiento a la veracidad, o reclamación de plagio o difamación del trabajo ganador, el participante queda obligado a hacer las aclaratorias correspondientes.

- Los jurados se reservan el derecho de retirar un premio si posteriormente sale a luz que el/la participante no cumplió con las condiciones de inscripción.
- El fallo del jurado es inapelable.
- La fecha límite para entregar los trabajos es el **30 de septiembre de 2009** y la ceremonia de **premiación se realizará el 15 de octubre de 2009.**

4.- Criterios de Evaluación

El trabajo será evaluado según:

A) su calidad técnica y valores estéticos;

B) su capacidad para transmitir y reflejar:

- pertenencia de ACINUPA al Sistema de Naciones Unidas, teniendo en cuenta que Panamá es sede de Oficinas Regionales y Subregionales de diferentes Agencias de NNUU;
- solidaridad, pluralidad y diversidad de nuestra comunidad;
- complementariedad Funcionario-Cónyuge o Pareja en sus distintos proyectos individuales y familiares.
- aporte profesional y personal de Cónyuges y Parejas dentro y fuera del Sistema de NNUU.

C) El jurado también aplicará criterios generales tales como: composición, iluminación, manejo del color, consideraciones éticas, originalidad, innovación y creatividad.

D) El jurado tendrá en cuenta el esfuerzo aplicado en la elaboración del trabajo.

Premio

El premio consistirá en una placa de ACINUPA con el logotipo de su autoría y un certificado para un fin de semana (de sábado a domingo) en un Hotel de lujo (2 personas).

Los autores de los cinco mejores trabajos presentados recibirán un certificado de participación y selección en el CONCURSO LOGO ACINUPA.

Ciudad de Panamá, 28 de agosto de 2009

Verónica Pereyra

Susana Vázquez

Chairperson

Encargada del Concurso LOGO ACINUPA

ACINUPA

ACINUPA

APPENDIX III

INFORMATION MANUAL COVER

BIENVENIDOS A PANAMÁ

MANUAL INFORMATIVO 2010

ACINUPA
Asociación de Cónyuges y Parejas de Funcionarios(as) Internacionales
de Naciones Unidas en Panamá

APPENDIX IV

INFORMATION MANUAL INDEX

1. INTRODUCCION

2. INFORMACIÓN SOBRE PANAMÁ

- 2.1. Clima
- 2.2. Economía
- 2.3. Gobierno
- 2.4. Historia
- 2.5. Religión
- 2.6. Educación
- 2.7. Índice de Desarrollo Humano (IDH)
- 2.8. Diferencias culturales
- 2.9. Panamá como Regional de las Naciones Unidas

3. REQUISITOS PARA TRASLADO Y UBICACIÓN

- 3.1. Visas
- 3.2. Documentos de identificación
- 3.3. Compra de automóviles (nuevos o usados)
- 3.4. Embarques
- 3.5. Servicio Nacional de Migración
- 3.6. Zonas residenciales
- 3.7. Corredores de bienes raíces
- 3.8. Alquiler o renta de bienes inmuebles
- 3.9. Compra de bienes inmuebles
- 3.10. Servicios básicos
- 3.11. Servicio doméstico
- 3.12. Salida de Panamá

4. ESTADÍA

- 4.1. Servicios de Asesores Legales
- 4.2. Servicios bancarios
- 4.3. Tarjetas de crédito
- 4.4. Seguridad
- 4.5. Compras
- 4.6. Transporte
- 4.7. Vida Social

5. CENTROS EDUCATIVOS

- 5.1 Centros de enseñanza preescolar
- 5.2 Colegios
- 5.3 Universidades
- 5.4 Centros de idiomas
- 5.5 Listado de Museos
- 5.6 Listado de sitios web actividades culturales

6. SALUD

- 6.1 Condiciones sanitarias
- 6.2 Emergencias y otros servicios
- 6.3 Médicos conocidos y recomendados por miembros de ACINUPA

7. ORGANIZACIONES

- 7.1. Organizaciones del Sistema de Naciones Unidas
- 7.2. Organizaciones No Gubernamentales
- 7.3. Embajadas y Consulados
- 7.4. Listado de sitios web de grupos de extranjeros en Panamá

8. CONCLUSION